

Deliverable 7.1

T-Factor Theory of Change

| DELIVERABLE TABLE

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INTRODUCTION

A **Theory of Change (ToC)** can be conceived as a tool that serves as the articulation of intended objectives, how you think the objectives will be achieved, and why you believe it to be so (Robert Penna, 2011). For example: *If we provide X support, we believe Y and Z will happen.* A ToC articulates the intended changes for people, issues, and systems. It helps make explicit the connections and logic between activities (e.g. what you will do in terms of deploying financial and nonfinancial contributions), outputs (the short-term, direct results), and outcomes and impacts (the longer-term shifts that occur for issues and contexts, either directly or indirectly).

The ToC is typically constructed by first identifying the desired long-term goals and then working backward from these to identify all the intermediary effects, or outcomes, that are intended to occur to demonstrate progress. The ToC includes the influence of the context you are working in, as well as the assumptions and evidence you are relying on.

A ToC carries several benefits (Brest, 2010; Brown, 2020; Jackson, 2013). First, it can help describe and interpret for all involved stakeholders what you are seeking to achieve and why. In this way, the ToC can serve as a communications tool to align and manage expectations. Adopting a high-level portfolio view of Theory of Change, it can also inform scoping decisions in terms of themes, instruments, and partnerships. Furthermore, it can identify gaps and issues that require further validation, as you prioritize how you seek additional research and evidence. A ToC should also inform the selection of methods, indicators, and standards that you can use to measure and evaluate success, while aligning short- and long-term measurement efforts.

A standard format for a Theory of Change does not exist (Social Impact Investment Taskforce, 2014). However, a typical way of developing and constructing a Theory of Change is the application of the **logic model framework**. This linear logical model explores the basic components that will eventually become a nonlinear Theory of Change.

The common components of the logic model are:

- **Inputs:** The financial and nonfinancial resources you bring. Examples include the amount and type of capital, instruments used, networks, time, and passion.

- **Outputs:** The immediate, direct results from deployment of these resources, including what is delivered, to whom, when, and how. Examples include the number of units or products sold, the number of users reached, or the demographic characteristics of the direct beneficiaries.
- **Outcomes:** The short-term and medium-term results attained or effects for individuals, groups, or issues. They can be both directly and indirectly related to resource deployment. Examples include improvements in targeted health behaviors for individuals or groups, or reduction in localized household-level economic poverty.
- **Impact:** The long-term changes achieved for populations, issues, or systems. Impacts usually also specify the nature of contribution from the deployed resources relative to other inputs and influential factors. Examples include the shifts in behaviors or patterns for multiple population groups, or reductions in regional poverty levels.
- **Assumptions:** Description of what you believe to be true in the context of the intended changes. They describe the basis of evidence or experience you are using, and should identify possible influential factors across the various levels from inputs to impacts.

The logic model is usually depicted as a **visual impact map**, read from left to right:

Figure 1: Visual impact map. Source: adapted from Logic model of measuring impact, impact measurement working group of the G8 Social Impact Investment Taskforce, 2014

The success of the logic model is largely due to its capacity to provide a valuable and effective tool not only to understanding change at a high level, but also to planning, monitoring and ultimately evaluating the interventions in practice.

An alternative, though certainly complementary approach to developing and describing the Theory of Change of an intervention has been proposed by Griffith University in 2020. This approach adopts a more narrative approach vis-à-vis the Theory of Change, which could be more appealing and easier to understand when practitioners are less acquainted with the Theory of Change.

An illustrative depiction of the impact map based on the Griffith University approach is presented below:

Figure 2: Elements of impact map. Source: adapted from Substation33 Impact Report 2020, Griffith University, 2020

In the context of T-Factor, we choose to use the Griffith approach for developing an overarching ToC that can describe the rationale of the project as a whole, by proposing new methodologies for innovative city making that leverage temporary uses throughout the so-called “waiting time” of urban regeneration¹, supporting a network of cities in experimenting and exchanging methodologies and their results. The use of the Griffith diagram helps us articulate the high-level T-Factor Theory of Change but also identify the different indicators that will be used to assess its results and evaluate its impacts. Furthermore, it provides a basis to reflect on the role of internal & external barriers and enablers in the realization of the project strategy and the achievement of the expected results. We anticipate that more granular **Theories of Change and impact maps** will be articulated for the T-Factor pilot cities, considering the specific contexts and circumstances, the prevalent challenges and opportunities, and the precise constellation of stakeholders involved at the local level.

¹ The “waiting time” is a key concept in T-Factor; we understand it as the time period that stands in between the approval of a masterplan or pre-masterplan on the one hand, and the delivery of the regenerated spaces and areas on the other hand, often years or decades later.

1. T-Factor's Theory of Change

1.1 A layered Theory of Change

We have developed an impact map that clearly articulates the Theory of Change – outlining what T-Factor does as a whole, which is a clear guide for how to weave an impact story. The model is based on the Substation33 Impact map from Griffith University with a combination of gained knowledge from the advanced cases study² and collaboration with the so-called Transformation Agency³. The design of the framework:

- Needs to be loose and adaptable enough to embrace the diversity of the T-Factor pilot cities and the targeted regeneration initiatives;
- Has to play a strategic role in the way the pilot cities make decisions over time around their meanwhile plans and activities, coherently with the broader regeneration process;
- Recognizes that T-Factor is a complex and multi-layered project where change is pursued at different levels, including the *micro* level of single, pace-based meanwhile activities with their own specific objectives that address local missions of innovation (that we call **“mission” level**); the *meso* level of the whole pilot intervention which mainly relates to the overall meanwhile programmes implemented in the pilot cities (that we call **“pilot” level**); the *macro* level of T-Factor as an international project that aims to foster transnational collaboration and co-creation of new knowledge and practices on the topic of meanwhile uses in urban regeneration (that we call **“transnational” level**).

The impact framework with clear indicators is meant to guide monitoring, evaluation and learning alongside the work of the pilots. Therefore, the core objective of the framework is to clearly express:

- The hypothesis that T-Factor makes about how change happens through the activities that are undertaken;

² Advanced Cases Portfolio (D2.1), published by the T-Factor project in May 2021.

³ In T-Factor, the Transformation Agency is a core project body that oversees and accompanies the pilot cities in the design and delivery of temporary use strategies

- The intentions, purpose and goals of T-Factor as a whole, across the three levels, and over time;
- The sequence of outputs towards outcomes so that T-Factor and the pilots can achieve the set goals.

Therefore, the impact map of T-Factor consists of two different parts. Firstly, the design and development of the framework aligns with the Theory of Change - i.e. what it does, how and for what purpose or intention. These are elements which T-Factor has control over. If T-Factor starts to make a change by undertaking certain activities, this will result in x and y . Secondly, the impact framework contains elements that T-Factor can influence, but has no direct control over – i.e. the outcomes to encounter hypothetically over time. It is possible to steer these outcomes based on the first results of activities. Moreover, the pilots can apply and modify this framework to create their own theory of change.

1.2 T-Factor Theory of Change

The figure below provides a visual overview of the T-Factor's Theory of Change based on the Griffith model (Figure 3):

Figure 3: T-Factor's Theory of Change based on the Griffith model

As we can see in the figure, T-Factor addresses a **core problem**, described as follows:

“Rigid, deterministic and infrastructure-only approaches to urban regeneration are less and less able to deal with rapid changes in our societies. We increasingly risk redevelopments unable to stand the time test, and with poor quality and value for the local communities.”

Therefore, T-Factor's Theory of Change is entirely articulated around the **opportunity** of *'leveraging meanwhile uses to equip urban regeneration with a better set of tools and methods to face uncertainty and unpredictability, while increasing chances to add (shared) value to the masterplanning and delivery process'*.

Accordingly, the logic concatenation of activities, outputs and outcomes is articulated alongside the three levels at which T-Factor is expected to trigger and achieve change:

- **Mission level** – the 'micro' level of meanwhile activities. Meanwhile activities across the pilot cities will follow a mission-oriented approach, articulating a portfolio of meanwhile interventions that, by embracing key masterplan and regeneration challenges, are meant to create the conditions for collective and collaborative engagement and experimentation in placemaking towards the creation of shared value.
- **Pilot level** – the 'meso' level of the masterplan and regeneration project. A systemic and synergistic design and orchestration of meanwhile placemaking programmes can go beyond specific results at single meanwhile intervention, triggering a deep transformation in the trajectories of masterplanning and regeneration processes towards higher quality spaces and longer term legacy.
- **Transnational level** – the 'macro' level of T-Factor. T-Factor's creation of knowledge, practices and capacity to unlock inclusive, thriving and regenerative urban environments through international collaboration, knowledge exchange and co-creation of new knowledge and practice in the field.

It is important to note that the distinction of the activities, outputs and outcomes are not strictly related to a certain level. The interconnection of the levels is one of the key challenges within the T-Factor project. For example, improved collaboration between local practitioners with the same missions is placed at mission level. However, this could eventually result in increased dialogue between different local practitioners and stakeholders which could affect the masterplan in the long run (pilot level).

In order to tackle the problem and leverage the opportunity, the **'if we'** of T-Factor (**what T-Factor will do**) is described as follows:

IF WE

At mission level

- Leverage temporary uses in the *waiting time* of urban regeneration to address **local, shared missions of innovation** that are relevant to sustainable development opportunities and challenges;
- Use temporary uses as a **testbed** to collaboratively explore and test co-creative solutions in address to the identified missions.

At pilot level

- Design and orchestrate **temporary use strategies as a portfolio of synergistic experiments** that address innovation missions with a systemic lens;
- Embrace a **prototyping & iterative placemaking** that allows to deliver temporary uses in sequences, observe interactions, and capture **strategic learning** in light of "permanent" uses, so as to improve masterplan value and regeneration process.

At transnational level

- Harvest and systematize a wide set of **resources and tools** on temporary uses, and for a wide variety of stakeholders;
- Foster **collaboration** between local urban regeneration practitioners, developers and a network of thematic international experts in urban planning and sustainability, which can inspire and support mission-oriented temporary uses in other regeneration projects;
- Develop **community-building processes** throughout the project to facilitate wide exchange of knowledge, practices and know-how on temporary uses in urban regeneration.

We then articulate below the activities of T-Factor across the three levels, which relate to the 'by' dimension of the Griffith model (**the activities that T-Factor proposes to undertake**):

BY***At mission level***

- **Mapping out** feelings, perceptions, values and challenges that different actors and stakeholders attribute to the area(s) under regeneration across the pilot cities, to understand leverage points for intervention through temporary use strategies;
- **Engaging and allying different actors around local missions** that address shared challenges and opportunities of urban regeneration, so as to pool a plethora of resources around common objectives and agendas of change;
- **Scoping out, designing and delivering co-creative meanwhile use programs** that leverage local missions to unfold innovative uses, functions and meanings;
- **Applying action research** to seize performance and progress over time, and to feed and steer ongoing discussion & exchange with developers and key regeneration stakeholders.

At pilot level

- **Establishing a Transformation Agency** in support to the design, delivery and critical observation of meanwhile use strategies;
- Creating a supporting infrastructure of **thematic labs (T-Labs)** which provides the pilots with knowledge, best practices, and know-how to unlock innovative meanwhile uses.

At transnational level

- **Mapping out and systematizing** temporary use initiatives, actors and existing regulations across Europe and beyond in order to document and disseminate emerging approaches and inspire new temporary initiatives;
- **Setting up a digital platform** that captures knowledge with clear visualizations of meanwhile stories from different cities;
- **Organizing knowledge sharing events** on different challenges and opportunities driven by temporary uses;
- Understanding the viability of **an international think tank** on temporary uses that can contribute to the spread and further development of these practices in the long run, especially via transferability to existing or future redevelopments across Europe.

Through the set activities, a wide range of **outputs** are expected to be achieved, as described below (non-exhaustive):

At Mission level

- **Wide range of stakeholders engaged** around shared innovation missions;
- **Diversity of stakeholders** and publics engaged;
- **Number of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) articulated** within innovation missions and targeted via various temporary uses;
- **Pooled** material (e.g. financial capital) and immaterial (e.g. human capital) **resources**;
- **New temporary services, products, programs and activities** that create **opportunities** for: sustainable lifestyles; affordable housing; active citizenship (volunteering, associations, etc.); life satisfaction; education & training; jobs & enterprises;
- **Diversity in temporary uses delivered** (e.g. from organizing festivals to establishing local sustainable restaurants) in response to different needs;
- **Citizens and stakeholders** actively **engaged in co-creation, co-production & co-management** of temporary uses in order to stimulate agency and legitimacy in placemaking while triggering innovation in uses, functions and meanings.

At Pilot level

- **Tested tools and methods** for designing and delivering meanwhile placemaking in urban regeneration;
- **Actual support** of the **Agency and T-Labs** to developers and local practitioners e.g. quantity or frequency of touchpoints, review between agency and pilots, type of mentoring tools and methods of placemaking;
- **Tested innovations** for regulating, governing and funding meanwhile uses in urban planning;

At Transnational level

- **International collaborations** established with local practitioners, international experts, T-Labs, Agency, etc.;

- Number of **events organized** to exchange knowledge; **resources created** and made available for a wide variety of stakeholders;
- Number of **participants and diversity of the audience** in the collaboration and network events, number of **platform subscribers** on the T-Factor platform, number of **stories created**;
- Level of interest to the T-Factor's Think tank model and commitment to its follow up.

And eventually the **outcomes** that T-Factor hypothesizes to likely unleash over time (non-exhaustive):

At Mission level

- Improved **multi-stakeholder and multi-actor collaboration** in the achievement of shared missions;
- Additional **funding** raised for temporary uses (short-term transactional sponsorship);
- Enhanced (peer to peer) **relational trust and social capital**;
- Enhanced **capacities and skills** across different audiences that foster employability, citizenship and, more broadly, human development within planetary boundaries;
- Enhanced **legitimacy and agency** in placemaking processes;
- **New & shared urban assets** that foster co-production, co-management and shared responsibility of urban spaces;
- New or renovated **commercial offers and new businesses** located in the area;
- **Income** opportunities;
- Improved space **accessibility & connectivity**;
- **New lifestyles** that embrace well-being and greener attitudes;
- Creation of **longer term job opportunities**;
- **Changed perceptions** of the area, particularly related to beauty, accessibility, safety and security, livelihood, creativity;
- Increased **property values and attractiveness** of the area.

At Pilot level

- Increased **dialogue** across different actors and stakeholders that contribute to **mitigate conflicts**;
- Enhanced **strategic capacity** to run masterplanning and regeneration processes through agile, iterative and testbed approaches;
- Shift in **developers' mindsets** towards new forms and processes of urban regeneration driven by co-creative engagement and social value generation;
- Perceived **mitigation of strategic risks** by developers and key regeneration stakeholders;
- Enhanced or reinforced **strategic partnerships** throughout the masterplanning and delivery process;

- Improved **project management culture, methods and tools** by developers and key regeneration stakeholders;
- Improved **decision making capacity and tools** for evidence based decision;
- More **diversified uses and functions** in the masterplan and enhanced room given to green and community functions as well as to services and uses of social interest;
- New **policies, regulations and funding mechanisms** that incentivize temporary use strategies;
- New **policies and strategies** that propel new opportunities for the pilot redevelopments to thrive in the long run (e.g. new policies and strategies in - for example - sustainable mobility, circular economy, resilience that allow the pilot regenerations to keep on investing in sustainable innovations);
- New forms of **co-governance and co-ownership** that keep on investing in the meanwhile use legacy;
- New forms of **co-investment and capital deployment** in support to sustainable and socially inclusive urban regeneration;

At Transnational level

- New and enhanced **knowledge** in urban regeneration that contributes to global challenges of sustainable urban development;
- New **initiatives and international projects** on temporary uses in urban regeneration that build on T-Factor's network, resources and tools created;
- Improved link between **theory & practice** in urban regeneration and placemaking;
- Growing dynamics of **international exchange**.

And **finally contribute** to:

- **Mission level:** the broad opportunity and/or problem on the mission-level which could be articulated into six thematic impact areas: Building communities, Cultivating innovation, Growing prosperity, Attaining sustainability, Making places and Improving quality of life;
- **Pilot level:** Enhanced strategic approaches, improved operational capacity and empowered relational system underpinning the regeneration process;
- **Transnational level:** New and tested blueprints for the socially and economically viable regeneration of European historic urban areas and cultural landscapes, with enhanced well-being and quality of life, social cohesion and integration. In the context of T-Factor, this impact domain is mainly related to eight core SDGs, as we will explain in the next section.

2. T-Factor General Impact Framework

In order to unpack the impact dynamics of T-Factor, the General Impact Framework is articulated around the three interlinked levels already presented in the previous section. Level 1 and 3 represents outputs and outcomes at respectively micro and macro level. Level 2 acts as a 'bridge' by allowing local processes and learnings of meanwhile interventions to be incorporated into the masterplan and enhance the capacities and capabilities of pilot owners. These can be shared and transferred across different cities in Europe thanks to the T-Factor platform, T-Labs, knowledge exchange events and more broadly through Communities of Practices approach and activities delivered by the project.

- The micro level (Level 1) – **mission level:** is centered on **the activities** that are undertaken in the context of meanwhile placemaking. The context and scale of reference is (strictly) **local and 'small'**, revolving around the site and its immediately affected stakeholders and local communities.
- The meso level (Level 2) – **pilot level:** is centered on the **masterplan/regeneration level**. The spatial scope is broader with effects reverberating throughout the regeneration area and the wider urban context, both in terms of design (the masterplan), people and developers.
- The macro level (Level 3) – **transnational level:** looks **beyond the masterplan**, understood as a meaningful contribution to the resolution of global challenges. The contextual scope is **no longer expressed in 'narrow' spatial terms**, but is rather conceived as **best practice** that may inspire others to take (similar) action.

It bears repeating that the three levels are **interconnected**, thereby creating a **multi-layered and dynamic impact framework**. This reflects the articulated strategy and logic of intervention of T-Factor which works at different levels to influence and enhance the urban regeneration knowledge and practice.

The visual below graphically represents the T-Factor General Impact Framework.

TEMPORARY USE STRATEGIES OF URBAN REGENERATION DRIVEN BY MISSIONS

Figure 4: T-Factor General Impact Framework

In the Impact Framework, **the mission level** is conceived as mission-driven meanwhile uses (missions in short). The mission is typically expressed in an evocative statement centered on the goals (outcomes) that give meaning, sense, and direction to agency; for example, improving the wellbeing and life opportunities of deprived teenagers in the community.

Missions always happen **through people** (Al Wear et al., 2014). On the one hand, **those who are directly or indirectly affected by the activities** (e.g. local/surrounding communities, users of buildings, spaces, and facilities, specific demographic/socio-cultural groups, business owners, civic organizations, etc). On the other hand, **those who affect the activities**, both in terms of **design** (e.g. public bodies and authorities, representatives of local/surrounding communities, developers) and **delivery** (e.g. professional consultants, project managers, contractors, developers, etc) of activities. Conceptually speaking, missions are geared towards **creating, scaling or accelerating positive impact** (e.g. green spaces, access to essential services, ...) and/or **preventing, detecting or mitigating negative impact** (e.g. poor air quality, noise pollution due to construction work, ...). In the reality of placemaking, the perspectives of opportunity (positive impact) and challenges (negative impact) typically overlap; not in the least because underpinning the intent towards positive impact, there are usually severe societal problems at root.

The **variety** of **missions** addressed via temporary uses can be expressed through different **impact themes**; they are the scope within/through which impact happens. Therefore, the specific impact framework at mission level consists of **six themes**, divided into a number of non-exhaustive sub-components:

Improving quality of life, including but not limited to:

- High quality, local healthcare and social services;
- Access to basic services such as food and water;
- Tolerance, respect and engagement with people from different cultures, backgrounds and beliefs;
- Low levels of crime and antisocial behavior;
- Equal opportunities to quality life.

Making places, including but not limited to:

- Transport facilities, including public transport, that help people travel within and between communities;
- Well-maintained, local, user-friendly public and green spaces with facilities for everyone (young and old);
- Sufficient range, diversity and affordability of housing within a balanced housing market;

- A high quality, well-designed built environment of appropriate size, scale, density, design and layout that reflect the local character of the community.

Attaining sustainability, including but not limited to:

- Efficient use of resources (e.g. energy efficiency, land, water resources, flood defense, waste minimization, recycling and circularity);
- Protecting and improving natural resources and biodiversity (e.g. air quality, noise, water quality, light quality);
- Addressing the challenges posed by the climate crisis (e.g. temperature and humidity); etc.

Growing prosperity, including but not limited to:

- A wide range of jobs and training opportunities;
- Stable income for a wide population;
- Attracting businesses with focus on local and sustainable supply chains;
- Dynamic business environment;
- A strong and diverse business community that links into the wider economy;
- Creation of entrepreneurial community with focus on heritage and culture; etc.

Cultivating innovation, including but not limited to:

- Enhancement of creativity and capabilities at organizational, enterprise and individual level;
- Development of skills of different stakeholders through education;
- Access to quality education and lifelong learning opportunities;
- Widely available and effective telecommunications and internet access.

Building communities, including but not limited to:

- Collaboration of different meanwhile interventions, strong community and voluntary associations (e.g. residents' associations, neighborhood watch);
- Civic values, responsibility and sense of belonging;
- Representative and accountable governance systems that enable inclusive, active and effective participation by individuals and organizations;
- Access to funding and capital resources for different publics and communities.

Figure 5: 'Impact Themes' at mission level

Furthermore, the **pilot level** captures the outcome of the T-Factor's city-making method on the masterplans and the regeneration process. In particular, the pilot level looks at the change achieved in terms of increased capacity of developers to address citizens' needs, foster shared ownership of the areas, promote socially and economically viable regeneration practices and foster the formation of valuable alliances oriented towards shared regeneration goals. Whatever type of activities the local coalitions execute at mission level, all the related regeneration and masterplan processes go through aspects which are related to strategic, operational and relational aspects. This **process** - through which activities happen, carries value in and of itself - expresses how outputs & outcomes are created and are crystallized along three dimensions:

- **Enhanced strategic approach:** these activities change, in a positive manner, the value of the masterplan. Examples include changes to the urban planning culture (e.g. fostering a culture of meanwhile uses, different mindsets, better reputation), changes to the masterplan itself (i.e. the institutionalization of meanwhile uses, return on investment, learnings), the way meanwhile uses are managed and orchestrated (e.g. through strategic partnerships, mitigated risks), etc.
- **Reinforced operational capacity:** these activities build and create better capabilities, capacity and resources among developers. Here the value takes a somewhat more tangible form, such as improved organizational capacity and project management, data driven decisions, team organization, better/more access to funding, tailored monitoring and evaluation approaches, and better regulation etc.
- **Empowered relational system:** these activities generate shared trust and value aimed at building engagement/empowerment of participants and/or collaboration/participation among participants and developers. The value is typically expressed through intangibles, such as better relational/social capital, greater trust and legitimacy, multi-stakeholder co-creation and co-governance etc.

Lastly, the **transnational level** refers to the impact of T-Factor in terms of fostering awareness, building and disseminating new knowledge for the meaningful management of the waiting time in urban regeneration for cities inside and or outside the country. The regeneration project should foster collaboration through the T-Factor network, develop community-building processes to facilitate exchange and make a wide set of resources and tools available for other regeneration projects.

In the general framework of T-Factor, the so-called **Transformation Labs (T-Labs)** are the fundamental engine that allows knowledge, learning and results achieved at mission level to scale up and contribute to knowledge creation and exchange at transnational level. In the project, the T-Labs work hand in hand with the Transformation Agency: while the latter is mainly a design task force that provides

the pilots with methods and tools to design, deliver and critically reflect on missions-driven meanwhile strategies, the Labs are instead thematic *hubs*; they support and accompany the pilots according to the themes they seek to address and innovations they aim to unleash through their innovation missions. Taken together, the Agency and the T-Labs form a supportive infrastructure for the pilot cities in order to experiment with mission-oriented meanwhile interventions and regeneration processes.

There are seven T-Labs in T-Factor:

- T-Lab1: Arts, Creativity, Culture
- T-Lab2: Urban production & Digitalization
- T-Lab3: Citizen-led Smartness
- T-Lab4: Urban Design Health and Well-being
- T-Lab 5: Circular & Collaborative Economy
- T-Lab 6: Social Innovation and Social Inclusion
- T-Lab 7: Climate Change and Regenerative Cities

Within the framework, the T-Labs are placed in the overlapping spheres, in order to **highlight the key thematic crossovers that they are likely to undertake, and therefore the main combinations of impact domains that each T-Lab may steer, alone or in cooperation with other T-Labs**. For example, T-Lab4 is placed at the intersection between ‘Making Places’ and ‘Quality of Life’, considering its focus on green and built environment interventions that can foster sociality, relationships, healthier lifestyles and green practices. Similarly, T-Lab 2 is placed at the intersection between ‘Growing Prosperity’ and ‘Cultivating Innovation’ based on its focus on creative makerspaces, making facilities and digital technologies that can contribute to both creative skills and urban environments, as well as to innovative jobs and enterprises in cultural and creative industries. Indeed, each T-Lab is likely to move beyond one or two impact “spheres”; however, the framework is meant to also help the Labs understand and visualise their own “entry point” to impact in T-Factor project, so as to further cooperate with the pilots in the selection of relevant indicators.

T-Lab 7 is placed at the very centre of the framework as it steers the general principles and values of T-Factor in direct relationship with the Horizon call (and broader programme) to which T-Factor responds to.

Figure 6: Top view impact framework integrated with the T-Labs

The transnational level is at a higher and final level anchored in and aligned with the outcomes expressed in the **United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**. The SDGs express a global call to action to make the world a better place by 2030. The 17 intertwined SDGs and 169 associated targets are interconnected. Specifically, for T-Factor, SDG 11 and 17 are placed central as they embrace the core goals of the T-Factor project, that are to contribute to sustainable cities and communities, and to strengthen international partnerships for this purpose. The other core SDGs that stand transversal in the T-Factor project are the following:

- Goal 3. “Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages”
- Goal 8. “Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all”
- Goal 9. “Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation”
- Goal 10. “Reduce inequality within and among countries”
- Goal 12. “Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns”
- Goal 13. “Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts”

These six SDGs are again relevant to the whole T-Factor and to the impact domains set by the Horizon 2020 call to which our project responds to. At the same time these SDGs, although to different extents and degrees, are highly relevant to the pilot cities and their own regeneration processes.

3. Impact Framework Indicators

The table below summarizes several potential indicators in light of the preliminary Impact Taxonomy. These are **preliminary indicators**, given that the ultimate selection of indicators will be informed by the meanwhile placemaking missions engaged in the Pilot Cities. Furthermore, the different themes and sub-themes could be transversally placed within the 3 levels – mission, pilot and transnational level. We did not include the differentiation between outputs and outcomes in order to simplify the indicative table. The table suggests indicators to track performance within different mission-oriented themes. At a later phase we can decide to make a distinction between outputs and outcomes together with the consortium. The indicator table is composed through use of various reputable sources and literature review, including the World Economic Forum’s metrics for ‘sustainable value creation’, the Doughnut Economics framework (as applied in cities like Amsterdam and Brussels), etc.

Mission level

<i>Improving quality of life</i>	Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of initiatives to give persons in the neighborhood coverage in terms of basic health services ● Number of sessions (workshops, events, public debates, etc.) to create awareness of consequences of tobacco, alcohol, drugs and obesity to number of individuals by sex, age and disadvantaged groups ● Higher accessibility of essential health services ● Enhanced well-being and quality of life <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Coming from events with topics related to work-life balance, healthy lifestyles and urban wellbeing ○ Coming from business models developed for sustainable and healthy urban lifestyles ● Age-standardized prevalence of current tobacco use among persons aged 15 years and older
	Safety & security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proportion of population that feel safe walking alone around the area they live during the meanwhile events ● Portion of parents that don't feel comfortable to let their children walk and play in the area without supervision ● Number of workshops for self-defense to a number of individuals by sex, age and disadvantaged groups ● % rate of crime rate before and after the regeneration project ● Proportion of persons victim of physical or sexual harassment, by sex, age and disadvantaged groups and place of occurrence, in the previous 12 months

	Food & basic services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of small-scale local food producers targeted, by sex and indigenous status, for the delivery of food and beverages for certain meanwhile interventions • Number of free food giveaways for underprivileged individuals • Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex, age and disadvantaged groups • Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity for underprivileged people, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)
	Diversity & Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of visitors who are refugees and other disadvantage groups, by sex and age • Average share of the built-up area of cities that is open space for public use for all, by sex, age and disadvantaged groups • Increase of diversity in the area • Proportion of population reporting having personally felt discriminated against or harassed in the previous 12 months on the basis of a ground of discrimination prohibited under international human rights law

Cultivating innovation	Learning / making / skilling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of (new) education centers in the area • Research and development initiatives and expenditures • Number of individual (online) courses offered for number of different persons by sex, age and disadvantaged groups • Number of patents filed, or number of inventions carried out • Number of people that successfully passed the online course and could integrate the knowledge into their daily or working life
	Creativity / capabilities / capacities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of events to promote education for youth not in education, employment or training • Portion of plans delivered to further sustain the innovation ecosystems as the project ends • Proportion of graduates of education programs • Number of offered trainings for bottleneck jobs • Extent to which (i) global citizenship education and (ii) education for sustainable development are mainstreamed • % of graduates that find a job, linked to the education, within a certain time period • Proportion of youth (aged 15–24 years) not in education, employment or training • Proportion of teachers with the minimum required qualifications, by education level

	Digitalization / Light Industrial Tech	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of individuals making online reservations • Number of developed applications • Number of light industry businesses occupy meanwhile spaces for their activity of new businesses per sector (# temporary and # permanent) • Good internet connection • Number of persons using an application to visit the area • Proportion of youth and adults with information and communications technology (ICT) skills, by type of skill • Light 'reindustrialization' enhanced in the area

Attaining sustainability	Biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of area under productive and sustainable agriculture • Official development assistance on conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity • Revenue increase generated and finance mobilized from biodiversity-relevant economic instruments
	Resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of acceleration/incubation programs address the circular/collaborative economy for delivering new products and services aimed at urban sustainability, wellbeing and quality of life • Number events (workshops, festivals, etc.) regarding resource use and use and consequences of single use plastics • Number of single use plastics consumed • Proportion of municipal solid waste collected and managed in controlled facilities out of total municipal waste generated • % less waste diverted from the area - responsible use of resources
	Noise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of noise cancelling technologies used in the area • Noise created by events / visitors of the area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Portion of complaints by inhabitants • Significant noise pollution decreases in the area
	Energy / Decarbonization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total greenhouse gas emissions per business or meanwhile intervention - if analyzed by scientific researchers • Proportion of population with primary reliance on clean fuels and technology • Portion of renewable energy sources of the area • Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption • Installed renewable energy-generating capacity

	Soil and air quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number events and workshops to enhance soil quality at people's home • Soil degradation due to constructions works and pollution • Indicators soil performance (soil moisture, soil organic matter, micro and macronutrients, soil PH and soil sanity) and air quality (Nitrogen oxides (NOx), sulphur oxides (SOx), particulate matter and other significant air emissions) - if analyzed by scientific researchers • Number of air treatment machines • Portion of workshops, raising awareness of consequences poor air quality
	Water management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water consumption and withdrawal in water-stressed areas (megaliters of water withdrawn, megaliters of water consumed) • % renewable water resources • Number events and visitors, by sex, age and disadvantaged groups, regarding water provisioning • Improvements of water waste in the area • Degree of integrated water resources management

Making places	(Built natural) + infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of events regarding nature loss and number of people targeted • Increase in forest area as a proportion of total land area • Increase in number of rooftops and the total surface of green rooftops • Increase in number of vegetable gardens and the total surfaces • Number of restored heritage buildings • Portion of initiatives to restore cultural heritage buildings • Number of new cultural and leisure facilities • Proportion of total government spending on essential services (education, health and social protection)
	Housing Place &	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of placemaking initiatives • Home ownerships of persons and students by sex, age and disadvantaged groups • Number of persons that find a new home, by sex, age and disadvantaged groups • Proportion of population with access to electricity and water • Availability of student rooms • Number of affordable houses • Raised value of the area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase in requests for renting or buying in the areas of x% compared to the forecasts of developers

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase in land value exceeds by x% the forecasts of developers made prior to the intervention <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ # new homes ■ # affordable homes
	Connectivity (virtual) mobility (physical) +	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Portion of mobility options to reach the area ● Number of alternatives for taking the car ● Proportion of population satisfied with their last experience of public transport ● Visitors, by sex, age and disadvantaged groups, taking public transport ● Enhancement of accessibility and connectivity of the region

Growing prosperity	Income	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proportion of visitors living in households with no access to basic services ● Number of initiatives to reduce poverty in the region ● Total official development grants from all donors that focus on poverty reduction as a share of the total funding of the regeneration project ● % income increase for the citizens inside and outside the neighborhood through various temporary uses
	Employment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Average hourly earnings of employees of the meanwhile interventions, by sex, age and disadvantaged groups ● Portion of schemes of work inclusion developed ● Decrease in unemployment rate, by sex, age and disadvantaged groups ● Jobs created and skills innovation opportunities identified in cultural and creative sectors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ # of innovative, challenge-driven trainings to prepare new professional figures in the cultural and creative field ○ # new forms of jobs/skills domains in the cultural and creative field - Temporary/permanent ○ # new forms of jobs/skills domains in another sector i.e. artist, artisans, bistro, café, restaurants, shops - Temporary/permanent
	Business / Enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Total revenue of different (meanwhile) companies ● Proportion of social enterprises vs. total enterprises ● Revenue increase of different companies ● Number of new businesses attracted

<p>Economic base / Circularity</p>	<p>Economic base / Circularity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of different businesses involved in the temporary interventions ● Portion of different activities per company ● Revenue of the meanwhile interventions compared to operating costs ● Extent of economic diversification ● Number of uses (% of total) developed, dedicated to the circular/collaborative economy ● Entrepreneurship created in heritage and culture-relevant field by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ # acceleration/incubation programs falling under the STEAM domain and tackling new heritage and culture-relevant products and services ○ # business models explored for innovative heritage and cultural products and services
	<p>...</p>	<p>...</p>
<p>Building communities</p>	<p>Engagement / participation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of people that feel connected to the area – sense of belonging ● Portion of citizens reached through meanwhile interventions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Within municipality and/or city or coming from outside the city ○ # of citizens reached through (social media) marketing/advertising ○ Unique vs frequent visitors ● Number of people in online community by sex, age and disadvantaged groups ● Amount visitor spending in the area ● Raised attractiveness of the areas for citizens and visitors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Unique vs frequent visitors ○ Growth rate of online community – retention rate and churn rate of the members ● Degree of stakeholder participation ● Number of different manners to engage # of different target groups, by sex, age and disadvantaged groups ● Portion of persons belonging to ‘vulnerable’ categories actively involved in upskilling/reskilling activities ● Diversity of target groups ● Enhanced legitimacy and agency in meanwhile placemaking processes - empowerment of different actors
	<p>Collaboration / Network</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Collaboration of different meanwhile interventions and partnerships with different local practitioners ● Trust and relational capital for collaboration between different actors ● Different marketing uses such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ # city officials engaged ○ # media partners activated ○ # external initiatives hosted

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ # of advertising signs in and around the city ● Raised interest over the areas by policy makers, social, cultural and economic stakeholders
	<p>Access to funding</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Diversity of financial resources available ● New funding streams attracted ● Dependency on lenders for operations temporary uses ● Amount of grants received, and amount generated by crowd funding initiatives ● Total per capita expenditure on the preservation, protection and conservation of all cultural and natural heritage, by source of funding (public, private), type of heritage (cultural, natural) and level of government (national, regional, and local/municipal)
	<p>...</p>	<p>...</p>

Pilot level

<i>Relational</i>	Relational capital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced trust & relational capital around redevelopment • Round tables and public debates <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Relationships with local institutions, organizations and associations ◦ Number of public debates ◦ Portion of workshops for the specific use of the area • Better dialogue and mitigated conflict
	Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of the population who have experienced a dispute in the past two years and who accessed a formal or informal dispute resolution mechanism, by type of mechanism • Total number of (new) policies • Portion of individuals that accessed the compliance-related policies and procedures • Number of whistle-blower complaints that include policy or procedure violation • Number of internal audits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ # of non-conformities with policies in each pilot country regarding redevelopment
	Co-creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of alternative management strategies recognized and analyzed • Increased social and cultural integration and cohesion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ # of cross-fertilization opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ # of participants (i.e. artist) sharing an area ■ # of partnerships developed with social economy organizations to develop upskilling/reskilling activities targeting vulnerable groups • Distributed agencies across pilots • Communities of practice
	Co-governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rights and responsibilities (rules of the game) clearly defined and adhered • Number of different individuals with decision power by sex, age and persons with and without disabilities • Recognition the decision of each member equitably • Legitimacy – to be able to exist and prosper in a society - precondition of business license to operate in society ranging from investments, committed stakeholders to political support and other stakeholders
Operational	Capital deployment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New forms of co-investment and capital deployment for urban regeneration • Improved support and increased investment over heritage and culture-relevant innovation

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ € X of additional funding raised to further enhance heritage, culture and creativity-led innovation in the targeted areas ○ # of different investors per meanwhile uses ○ # innovation missions tackled leveraging heritage, culture and creativity ● Amount of impact investing raised ● Dependency on lenders for adjustments masterplan
	Project management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tested tools and methods for designing & delivering meanwhile placemaking in urban regeneration ● Better decision making of developers ● Data driven decisions ● Number of innovative tools used by developers in the masterplan ● Resource capacity of the regeneration project - # of individuals working on the project multiplied by the % of time available ● Budget variances – variance actual budget from the project budget ● Number of project milestones integrated in the regeneration project
	Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of monitoring systems to ensure minimization of damage caused by the regeneration project and optimize opportunities ● Appropriate penalties assessed and collected for non-compliance ESG matters ● Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor urban planning
	Capacities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Training or research needed for the regeneration project ● Actual support delivered by the Agency/Labs to developers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mentioning the type of methods and tools used, ○ Quantity/frequency of touchpoints and reviews between agency and pilots etc. ● Frequency of touchpoints between agency and pilots ● Enhanced capacity and knowledge of developers ● Multidisciplinary teams ● 360° feedback from and to local practitioners, investors, developers, beneficiaries, etc.
Strategic	Planning culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promotion of regeneration projects with focus on ESG themes and cultural heritages ● Fostering culture of temporary uses in regeneration projects ● Enhanced reputation of the masterplan ● Different mindsets ● Enable urban planning culture

	<p>Changes to masterplan</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promote flexible masterplan ● Agreed and modified masterplans (new uses and positionings) ● Number of different stakeholders included in the changes in masterplan, by sex, age and persons with and without disabilities ● Portion of request for modification masterplan ● Nomadic approach of urban planning – engagement, conversation and a more dynamic, responsive approach to urban planning ● Support permanent adaptive functions ● (S)ROI and other metrics
	<p>Strategic Partnerships</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of partnerships between different stakeholders ● Political support obtained and maintained ● Long lasting partnerships between developers, policy makers, governments, etc. ● Mitigation of risks ● Synergies of resources ● Increased revenue through partnerships ● Partner engagement

Transnational level

<p>Awareness and knowledge T-Factor project</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of international collaborations and partnerships established ● Knowledge exchange events realized: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Webinars, discussions, brainstorm sessions, etc. ○ # of participants of different countries, by sex, age and persons with and without disabilities ● Knowledge and practical resources created, made available and accessed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Human, social and environmental capital ● Number of persons registered in the IT platform of T-Factor and regeneration projects, by sex and age ● Meanwhile interventions and urban regeneration stories created <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ # of people reached ● Awareness and improved knowledge for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Developers at other urban regeneration projects inside or outside the country ○ Beneficiaries ○ Governments and local authorities
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- Number of innovative new regeneration projects with a direct or indirect link to temporary uses
- New international projects on TU in urban regeneration
 - % similarity of masterplan
 - # of different stakeholders and developers
- Inspired new knowledge and raised interest by external regenerations
 - Tested blueprint developed for socially and economically viable regeneration, fully validated by the x pilots and made freely accessible for other developers and stakeholders across Europe and beyond

4. The framework applied

To check the prima facie usefulness of the T-Factor General Impact Framework, we applied the Framework to a well-documented Advance Case Study (ACS): **Manifattura Tabacchi (MT) in Florence**. Doing so, we recast the ACS of MT as ‘impact story’ narrated through the Impact Framework:

The overall objective of MT is to create a new city center outside the historic center, from a geographical and cultural point of view, as it was closed for more than 17 years. The three documented meanwhile uses carried their own missions, as part of the broader regeneration project. Firstly, ‘**Summer 2018**’ was a program of different events, initiatives, and laboratories in the summer of 2018. The aim was to bring the attention of citizens and communities back to MT and communicate the forthcoming transformation as a new contemporary pole in the city. Secondly, ‘**Building (B9)**’, a multifunctional space, opened in 2019, is the actual kickstart of the regeneration process. The space served as a prototype of the contemporary civic center, with the opportunity to experiment what the permanent Factory - where all the creative energies are activated (art, culture, design, hospitality) and will find a final expression - will look like and work. Lastly, ‘**Not a Museum (NAM)**’, an interdisciplinary program started in 2020, aimed to promote experimentation and production in contemporary arts and sciences and was conceived as a prototype for final use within the renovated MT.

The three levels in the T-Factor General Impact Framework can be readily retrieved:

The **mission level**, which is centered on the meanwhile activities itself with outputs and outcomes (both presented in a non-exhaustive fashion):

- Summer 2018: the temporary use entailed the organization of various events such as the Open Day, round tables with citizens, festivals such as Festival au Desert, Florence Folks, God is green, etc. These events brought the attention back to the local citizens as a symbolic institution for the city and as a place experiencing a deep transformation towards a contemporary pole promoting new “ahead of times” lifestyles. It helped to re-create a community linked to the site, free to access the spaces, to express preferences and issues in open dialogue with the property, and to live the transformation process in a proactive way.

- B9: various initiatives were launched, such as 4 ateliers and 4 laboratories set up in an ad hoc manner for the makers, a cafeteria, a bistro, a craft beer tasting area, an outdoor courtyard equipped with a stage for shows, an Italian music festival, temporary installations and exhibitions from contemporary artists, etc. The temporary use B9 proved to be a successful marketing product, as it has been able to attract many artists, artisans, bistro, café, restaurants, shops, willing to open their activity inside the spaces of MT, given the high number of requests. The makers, working closely and inside the same space, benefited considerably from the physical proximity that made it possible to exchange inputs, expand their networks, and get in contact with important personalities in the contemporary art and cultural sector.
- NAM: several events and festivals were organized, for instance LUCIA La Radio al Cinema, a festival dedicated to Italian and international radio works and podcasts etc. Despite COVID-19, the MT has been able to keep on attracting visitors and people through NAM, by reinventing partially the initial offer from exhibitions and other events in place towards more digital experiences. Unlike B9, NAM is not a fundamental marketing driver for attracting prospective tenants. In fact, while NAM has the ambition to install a permanent space for contemporary art inside the future “Factory”, it has not yet found investors willing to do so. However, it is still too early to make clear evaluations of this specific aspect.

The **pilot level**, which is centered on the pilot and/or masterplan level, the outputs and outcomes on the process is the following (presented in a non-exhaustive fashion):

The **process** of placemaking with temporary uses, is guided through a well-defined governance structure. This governance structure – principally between the property owner (MDTDM) and the organization running meanwhile activation (MIM) – is quite vertically conceived: MDTDM sets the strategy and the annual objectives and MIM acts as a supplier. More broadly and strategically, MIM acts as a connector with external partners and holds responsibility over the budget, making sure it is being deployed and managed in an efficient and transparent manner. At the same time, the daily division of work between MDTDM and MIM turned out to be rather non-hierarchical; in reality, the MIM team was responsible and involved in different tasks in a very open and collaborative way with serendipitous conversations (**relational**). Throughout the period of meanwhile interventions, the MIM team did not only track performance indicators, such as attendance numbers and revenue figures, but also engaged in a substantial documentation effort of each event (**operational**). Moreover, the team has worked through a multidisciplinary approach, engaging and leveraging skills and expertise ranging from communication and marketing, event management with focus on contemporary art, community engagement and hosting, identity management and design, account management, and security and safety management. The positive experience of meanwhile interventions may ultimately affect the masterplan (**strategic**).

Among the contributions of the meanwhile uses to the masterplan, the prototyping in B9 is considered the most successful. It was conceived as the heart of Manifattura in which creative energies find a final expression. Meanwhile use has been an effective means for experimenting new functions and uses to be finalized in the permanent project. However, the main challenge for the future is fully realizing the shift from temporary to permanent.

The **transnational level**, which goes beyond masterplan with long-term impacts and best practices (non-exhaustive):

In general, the time frame since the reopening of MT is too short to talk properly of impact and sharing knowledge of best practices of meaningful management of the waiting time in urban regeneration between different cities. However, indications of long-term transformations can be observed. The area has progressively experienced an increase in population, which in fact brought substantial increase in the perceptions of safety, social opportunities, and quality of life in the neighborhood. Subsequently, more and more restaurants and cafés were drawn to the area. Moreover, there are some initial positive signals of a real estate market's re-evaluation with an increase in the number of investors expressing an interest in developing regeneration projects in the surrounding area(s). However, some negative effects can be perceived as well. An overall increase in flows of people circulating in the neighborhood have implied difficulties in terms of mobility and parking. The overall economic development of the area implied an increase in prices in the neighborhood – e.g. for instance prices of houses and at restaurants – which could be the starting point of a general revaluation of the area and thus possible gentrification dynamics.

Finally, **SDGs** can be profiled in connection with the documented experiences in the MT Advance Case Study, for example:

- SDG 8: Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all. More specifically, target 8.5, to achieve full employment and decent work for all women and men by 2030. Target 8.6, with the aim to substantially reduce the proportion of youth not in employment, education or training.
- SDG 9: Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation. Specifically, MT contributes to target 9.1 with the development of quality, reliable, sustainable and resilient infrastructure to support economic development and human well-being, with a focus on affordable access for all. Furthermore target 9.2 is activated with the promotion of inclusive and sustainable industrialization.
- SDG 11: Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable. MT aligns with target 11.1, 11.3 and 11.4 which respectively ensure access to safe and affordable housing, improve inclusive and sustainable urbanization, and support efforts to protect cultural and natural heritages.

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